

GENETIC RISK FACTORS FOR OPIOID DEPENDENCE

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Abstract: This study aimed to fill a gap in the literature by shedding light on the genetic risk factors that contribute to opioid dependence, which previous studies have overlooked. Furthermore, the review of epidemiological data shows that opioid dependence is a global trend, with significant consequences for social, economic, and health care systems. This study applied a probit regression model, and the results revealed a significant positive impact on opioid dependence from cancer, cardiovascular disease, human genetic variations, and age. The findings from the Kendall correlation indicate a weak and significant positive correlation with health, socioeconomic, and genetic risk factors, such as cancer, blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, age, and human genetic variation in the United States. The Kendall correlation also revealed a weak significant positive correlation between human genetic variation and the prevalence of cancer, cardiovascular disease, and opioid dependence among the participants. This suggests that a higher level of genetic variation is associated with a higher risk of cancer, cardiovascular disease, and opioid dependence, thereby identifying individuals at risk of these conditions. Therefore, it is crucial to establish a sustainable control policy that identifies individuals with genetic risk factors that contribute to a high level of opioid dependence and to administer effective opioid treatment to prevent further degeneration of this problem.

Keywords: Genetic risk factors, Opioid dependence, Probit regression, Kendall correlation

Introduction

Opioids, while frequently given for pain relief, are also prone to abuse because of their addictive nature (Smith et al., 2017). Opioid dependency and addiction are synonymous, and there has been a consistent increase in the use of both prescribed and non-prescribed opioids over the past decade, leading to widespread substance abuse among adults (Fischer et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2019). Opioids are potent and highly addictive opiates that are commonly used for pain management. However, misuse frequently results in tolerance, dependence, and overdose. Opioid addiction is a persistent psychiatric disorder characterized by recurring periods of relapse and remission. Individuals affected by this condition endure several distressing symptoms, such as tolerance and withdrawal, over the course of their lives (APA & DSM, 2013). Opioid addiction is less prevalent than smoking and alcohol consumption, but it has significantly impacted health care systems and the criminal justice system (Grant et al., 2015; Jamal et al., 2014). The United States incurs billions of dollars in expenses each year because of the opioid crisis, primarily caused by the recent epidemic of prescription opioids. Using drugs to treat opioid addiction can

be crucial for preventing relapse and helping addicted individuals achieve stability, allowing them to work and maintain longer periods of abstinence (Douaihy et al., 2013).

While numerous factors can contribute to human diseases, familial history frequently emerges as a prominent risk factor for prevalent disease complexes, such as cancer, cardiovascular disease (CVD), diabetes, autoimmune disorders, and psychiatric illnesses (Benton et al., 2021). Individuals receive a full complement of DNA from both parents, along with several cultural and socioeconomic experiences from their families. Family history is considered a reliable indicator of an individual's susceptibility to certain diseases because family members closely reflect the distinct genetic and environmental factors that an individual encounters (Skov, 2020). The presence of inherited genetic variations within families significantly contributes to both the direct and indirect development of opioid dependency (Timpson et al., 2018). Various small-scale investigations conducted in North America have reported divergent conclusions regarding the addiction profile. According to Sixto-Costoya et al. (2021), 82% of users are male. In addition, 55% of users fall within the age range of 31 to 40. According to the research, there is evidence that women may abuse prescription opioids as much as, if not more than, men. This may be because women are more likely to report being dependent on opioids than men, as suggested by Green et al. (2009).

Studies conducted in the United States have shown that European individuals suffering from chronic pain are at greater risk of developing opioid addiction. This risk is higher among those who are prescribed high-dose opioids, are younger, male, have lower education levels, and have a personal or family history of substance abuse, including smoking. Additionally, individuals who have experienced childhood trauma or psychiatric illness are also more susceptible to opioid addiction (Rikard et al., 2023). The prevalence of nonmedical use of prescription opioids (POs) is highest among individuals aged 18–25 years, whereas the mortality rate of PO overdoses is highest among those aged 45–54 years. Among different racial and ethnic groups, non-Hispanic whites have a mortality rate that is three times greater than that of Hispanics and African Americans (Rikard et al., 2023). The aim of this study was to examine how genetic risk factors, along with health and socioeconomic indicators, contribute to opioid dependence.

Literature review and hypothesis development

Various factors have been linked to a higher likelihood of developing opioid dependence, although the degree to which they contribute differs among individuals (Yiannakopoulou, 2015). When assessing risk variables, it is crucial to acknowledge that causation is not always definitively shown in the studies that have been reported. Therefore, the data should be interpreted with caution (Foglia et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is important to differentiate between risk variables that contribute to substance use and those that contribute to substance dependence or abuse (Foglia et al., 2021; Vaughan, 2020).

The number of risk variables that children are exposed to has been directly linked to the development of substance dependence, in addition to the risk factors themselves (Wymbs et al., 2014; Bozzini et al., 2021). Although several longitudinal and cross-sectional investigations have been undertaken in this field, extensive studies are not particularly prevalent. Research indicates that several characteristics increase the risk for teenagers, such as engaging in antisocial behavior at an early age, experiencing depression and anxiety, struggling academically, having a low socioeconomic position, being involved in delinquent activities, experiencing physical or sexual abuse, exhibiting hyperactivity, and having a family history of chemical dependence (Ronel & Levy-Cahana, 2011; Wahid et al., 2021). Furthermore, higher levels of religious engagement, an earlier age at initial substance

use, a history of mental issues, or lower academic achievement are likely to contribute to an increased frequency of substance use (Ransome et al., 2019).

In addition to societal and familial factors, inherent biological and behavioral factors can contribute to an individual's susceptibility to developing substance use disorders. Biological mechanisms and specific genetic variations have been linked to the development of dependence (Chiarella et al., 2023). Psychological traits such as the need for rewards or sensations, decision-making abilities, lack of behavioral control, and impulsiveness are important factors that contribute to dependence (Chiarella et al., 2023; Kozak et al., 2019). Research conducted through family, twin, and adoption studies has repeatedly found that genetic variables play a significant role in the development of dependency behavior and relapse after treatment. These genetic factors interact with contextual factors to influence outcomes (Willoughby et al., 2021). Research on individuals with substance-related problems and their relatives has found strong connections between different categories of drugs and genetic and environmental factors that contribute to addiction (Barr et al., 2022). Based on the above considerations, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: Genetic risk factors significantly contribute to opioid dependence.

H2: Health and socioeconomic indicators significantly influence opioid dependence.

Methodology

Cross-sectional chromosome data were collected from the human genetic variation database (HGVD) in 2023 using genotype profiles from the United States. Samples of 750 human genotypic variations were collected along with other health and socioeconomic factors for this study. Quantitative methods like summary statistics, probit regression models, and Kendall's Tau-b were adopted for the analysis of this study. The probit regression model is suitable because the dependent variable, opioid dependence, is dichotomous among categories, indicating 1 for opioid dependence and 0 for non-opioid dependence. The probability regression model is a non-parametric test; thus, no stringent assumptions like those of parametric OLS, are needed. However, post-estimation tests such as the goodness of fit test, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC Curve), and sensitivity and specificity tests are required to validate the accuracy and reliability of the fitted probit regression model. The probit regression model can be specified as follows:

$$\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \hat{y} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{FH} + \beta_2\text{Cancer} + \beta_3\text{BP} + \beta_4\text{CVD} + \beta_5\text{HGV} + \beta_6\text{Age} + \varepsilon \dots \dots (1)$$

Where \hat{y} is the likelihood of opioid dependence, which is the dependent variable, and the independent variables include family history (FH) with two categories of having family history or none. Cancer was measured using count data for cases of cancer, blood pressure (BP) was measured using mmHg, cardiovascular disease (CVD) was measured using count data, human genetic variation (HGV) was measured in percentage, and age was measured in years. The β_0 is the constant term, and the β_1 to β_6 are the coefficient estimates of the independent variables, while the ε is the stochastic error term.

This study employs the Kendall Tau-b method as a nonparametric approach to explore the association between variables of interest, like opioid dependence, human genetic variation, family history, cancer, blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, and age. This method allows you to examine the direction and strength of the relationship between these variables. The critical values of 1 and +1 bound the correlation coefficient (T_b).

Results and discussion

Table 1: Summary statistics

	Mean		Std. Deviation
Cancer	120.74		32.019
Blood Pressure	68.98		19.509
CVD	31.96		7.927
HGV	0.47		0.332
Age	33.17		11.708
			Percentage
		Frequency	
Opioid dependence	0	490	65.33
	1	260	34.67
	Total	750	100.0
Family history	0	432	57.60
	1	318	42.40
	Total	750	100.0

Source: Authors’ computation using STATA software.

Table 1 shows that the average number of cancer cases was approximately 121, with a variability of approximately 32 cases. The average blood pressure was approximately 69 mmHg, with a variability of approximately 20 mmHg. The average number of cardiovascular disease cases was approximately 32, with a variability of approximately 8. The average genetic variation is approximately 0.5%, with a variability of approximately 0.3%, and the average age is approximately 33 years, with a variability of approximately 12 years. Individuals with opioid dependence comprised 260, representing 34.67%; individuals without opioid dependence or addiction comprised 490, representing 65.33%; individuals with a family history of opioid dependence comprised 318, representing 42.4%; and individuals without a family history of opioid dependence comprised 432, representing 57.6%.

Table 2: Probit regression model

Opioid dependence	Coefficient	S.E.	Z	P-value
Family history	-0.224	0.109	-2.06	0.039

Cancer	0.018	0.002	9.86	0.000
Blood Pressure	-0.007	0.003	-2.43	0.015
CVD	0.048	0.008	6.27	0.000
HGV	0.377	0.161	2.34	0.019
Age	0.021	0.005	4.53	0.000
Constant	-4.543	0.376	-12.08	0.000
Goodness of fit test				0.0612
Overall P-value	0.0000			

Source: Authors' computation using STATA software.

The probability value of the overall probit regression model in Table 2 is 0.0000, indicating statistical significance at a level lower than 1%. This indicates that the model has a high level of statistical significance (significance level = 1%). Health and socioeconomic factors, such as cancer, high blood pressure, heart disease, and age, as well as genetic risk factors, like genetic variation and family history, have a substantial impact on the probability of developing opioid dependence. Table 2 shows that the coefficient estimates for family history and blood pressure had a significant negative effect on opioid dependence. Therefore, an increase in family history and high blood pressure will decrease opioid dependence. On the other hand, the coefficient estimates for cancer, cardiovascular disease, human genetic variation, and age are statistically significant at the 1% and 5% levels, respectively. These factors have a significant positive impact on opioid dependence, indicating that increased health, socioeconomic, and genetic risk factors will contribute to a rise in opioid dependence in the United States. These findings support the research of Ronel and Levy-Cahana (2011), Wahid et al. (2021), Barr et al. (2022), and Chiarella et al. (2023). The findings corroborated the research hypothesis that genetic risk factors play a substantial role in opioid dependency (H1), whereas health and socioeconomic indicators exert considerable influence on opioid dependence (H2).

However, the goodness-of-fit test showed that the probability value of 0.0612 was higher than the significance threshold of 0.05. This suggests that the probit regression model is a suitable fit for the dataset. Furthermore, Figure 1 shows the ROC curve, which exhibits an accuracy value of 0.8293, indicating a model accuracy of 82.93%. This result confirms the accuracy and suitability of the model.

Figure 1: Area under the curve (ROC Curve)

Table 3: Nonparametric correlations

		Family history	Cancer	Blood Pressure	CVD	HGV	Age	Opioid dependence	
Kendall's Tau-b	Family history	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.038	.002	-.030	-.046	-.014	-.098**
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750
	Cancer	Correlation Coefficient	-.038	1.000	.154**	.151**	.061*	.194**	.385**
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750
	Blood Pressure	Correlation Coefficient	.002	.154**	1.000	.200**	.021	.245**	.115**
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750
	CVD	Correlation Coefficient	-.030	.151**	.200**	1.000	.097**	.087**	.251**
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750
	HGV	Correlation Coefficient	-.046	.061*	.021	.097**	1.000	.033	.141**
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750
	Age	Correlation Coefficient	-.014	.194**	.245**	.087**	.033	1.000	.255**
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750
	Opioid dependence	Correlation Coefficient	-.098**	.385**	.115**	.251**	.141**	.255**	1.000
		N	750	750	750	750	750	750	750

The asterisks ** and * represent the 1% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Table 3 demonstrates that opioid dependence has a weak and significant positive correlation with health, socioeconomic, and genetic risk factors, such as cancer, blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, age, and human genetic variation, suggesting that the higher the health, socioeconomic, and genetic risk factors, the higher the opioid dependence in the United States, which is consistent with the findings of Barr et al. (2022) and Chiarella et al. (2023). Table 3 also shows a weak significant positive correlation between human genetic variation and cancer, cardiovascular disease, and opioid dependence. This suggests that the higher the human genetic variation, the higher the risk of cancer, cardiovascular disease, and opioid dependence among the individuals studied, thereby identifying those at risk of opioid dependence.

Conclusion and policy implications

Several studies have examined genetic risk factors in various dimensions of the chromosomes and genes of living offspring. However, this study aimed to bridge the existing gap by examining the role of genetic risk factors, together with health and socioeconomic factors, in opioid dependence. The analysis revealed that the average number of cancer cases was approximately 121, with a variability of approximately 32 cases. The analysis showed that the average number of cancer cases was approximately 121, with a variability of approximately 32 cases. The average blood pressure was approximately 69 mmHg, with a variability of approximately 20 mmHg. The average number of cases of cardiovascular disease was approximately 32, with a variability of 8. The average human genetic variation was approximately 0.5%, with a variability of approximately 0.3%. The average age was approximately 33 years, with a variability of approximately 12 years. The percentage of individuals without opioid dependence or addiction was 34.67%, the percentage of individuals with a family history of opioid dependence was 318 (42.4%), and the percentage of individuals without a family history of opioid dependence was 432 (57.6%).

More research using probit regression has shown that age, cancer, heart disease, and genetic variations have a significant positive effect on opioid dependence. This indicates that increased health, genetic, and socioeconomic risk factors will likely contribute to the rise in opioid dependence in the US. The Kendall correlation results show a weak but significant positive relationship with health, socioeconomic, and genetic risk factors like cancer, high blood pressure, heart disease, age, and genetic variation in humans. This indicates that the greater the number of health, socioeconomic, and genetic risk factors, the more people in the United States are dependent on opioids. Correlation analysis also revealed a weak positive correlation between human genetic variation and individuals with cancer, cardiovascular disease, and opioid dependence. This suggests that higher levels of human genetic variation are associated with higher rates of cancer, cardiovascular disease, and opioid dependence among the study population, thereby identifying individuals at risk of opioid dependence.

Therefore, a long-term control policy is necessary to identify individuals with genetic risk factors that increase their likelihood of becoming highly dependent on opioids and to provide them with effective opioid treatment to prevent the problem from worsening.

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